

DECICE

DEVICE-EDGE-CLOUD INTELLIGENT COLLABORATION FRAMEWORK

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D5.2 Development Environment Specification

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Executive Summary

The deliverable titled "Development Environment Specification", led by E4, provides a complete description of the environment that will host the framework, including software and hardware specification. It delves into the infrastructure design for the DECICE project. The document delineates key elements, including hardware specifications, middleware selection, bare metal provisioning, CI/CD toolchains, virtualization strategies, and containerization approaches.

The chosen hardware configuration is carefully detailed in the document. It represents a significant milestone in resource alignment with the project objectives. This includes master nodes, worker nodes, GPU nodes, IoT/Edge devices, and an Ethernet switch, each tailored to meet specific computational demands and facilitate seamless operation.

Middleware software, an essential development environment component, was selected based on scalability, flexibility, and compatibility with containerization technologies. Foreman, Jenkins, GitLab, and OpenStack emerged as critical tools for provisioning, CI/CD automation, version control, and cloud computing.

Bare metal provisioning and node recovery strategies were outlined, with Foreman identified as a robust infrastructure management tool capable of automating server deployment and configuration. Concurrently, Jenkins and GitLab were designated as pivotal components of the CI/CD toolchain, streamlining application testing, building, and deployment processes.

Virtualization strategies were explored, with OpenStack identified as the preferred platform for providing infrastructure as a service (IaaS) in private and public clouds. Kubernetes and K3s emerged as leading container orchestration platforms, offering automation, scalability, and management capabilities for containerized applications.

In conclusion, the description of this hardware and software ecosystem marks a pivotal step toward the final and complete realization of project objectives.

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1 Purpose and Scope of the Deliverable

This deliverable aims to provide a detailed specification of the hardware and software required by the DECICE framework. A complete description will be fundamental to proceed with implementing the framework. The hardware and software infrastructure will be available to fully integrate the DECICE components. In addition, it will be used to test and evaluate performance metrics.

This deliverable was developed in alignment with other Work Packages. In particular:

- WP2 in order to collect the hardware requirements for the AI scheduler.
- WP4 for the software and hardware requirements needed by the CI/CD process.

E4 (leader of the Work Package) leads this task and collects information and contributions from all partners by actively interacting with other Work Packages.

2 Abstract

Deliverable D5.2 is a comprehensive guide to the envisioned ecosystem for the DECICE framework. The primary objective is to provide a detailed description of the environment that will be the foundation for the implementation of various project components.

We present a complete exploration of the resources requisite for the developmental, testing, and validation phases. We delve into the description of hardware infrastructure, middleware software, bare metal provisioning, CI/CD toolchain, virtualization, and containerization. This was possible thanks to the alignment with WP2, WP3 and WP4.

In this deliverable, we describe the private cloud we will deploy. We want to ensure a dynamic and versatile cloud environment; we do so by making sure that the hardware setup includes master nodes, worker nodes, GPU nodes, and IoT/Edge devices, meticulously chosen for flexibility and scalability. We foresee middleware tools like Foreman for bare metal provisioning and Jenkins/GitLab for CI/CD pipelines streamline development workflows. OpenStack serves as the virtualization platform, providing robust infrastructure management capabilities. Kubernetes (K8s) and K3s are considered for containerization, offering automated deployment and management of containerized applications. Collectively, these components form a versatile and efficient development environment tailored to meet the diverse needs of the DECICE project.

This is a pivotal element in the DECICE infrastructure. A private cloud will allow partners to rapidly test and deploy their models without having the constraints and rules imposed by public cloud providers.

3 Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section Task T5.2 of the project plan. In particular, we discuss the composition of the private cloud that will be implemented and will be made available to project partners. The environment described will be used for the development, testing, and validation of the DECICE framework.

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
(O1) Develop a solution that allows to leverage a compute continuum ranging from cloud and HPC to edge and IoT.	This deliverable describes the development environment in which the solution will be implemented and tested, with a specific focus on (private) cloud resources that will be made available.
(O2) Develop a scheduler supporting dynamic load balancing for energy-efficient compute orchestration, improved use of green energy, and automated deployment.	Thanks to the resources described in the present deliverable, it will be possible to train the scheduler and test it on a real computing infrastructure.
(O3) Design and implement an API that increases control over network, computing and data resources.	The present deliverable outlines the infrastructure of the private cloud system that will allow the designed API to control its resources.
(O4) Design and implement a Dynamic Digital Twin of the system with AI-based prediction capabilities as integral part of the solution.	The AI-based prediction will be trained on the computational resources described in this deliverable.
(O5) Demonstrate the usability and benefits of the DECICE solution for real-life Use Cases.	The system described in the present deliverable will provide the DECICE framework with all the computational elements needed to simulate real-life Use Cases.
(O6) Design a solution that enables service deployment with a high level of trustworthiness and compliance with relevant security frameworks.	The deliverable describes tools to deploy the system seamlessly. Such tools will be installed on the hardware and will be available to use automatically. The basic steps to use them are explained in this deliverable as well.

4 Difficulties encountered

As discussed in Deliverable 5.1, partners have various perspectives and backgrounds. Designing a complete environment that suits all the possible desires requires maintaining a stable alignment between partners across all technical Work Packages. Moreover, the objective was to optimize the selection of computational resources. This becomes a challenge when considering the complexity and heterogeneity of the environment. Finding a shared vision was fundamental for the future of the project. Also, determining whether a unified infrastructure should serve Use Case implementation and other project needs posed another significant decision point. Concerning resource selection, partners exhibited differing views on the necessary system performance, as well as computing and networking requirements, leading to some ambiguity. It took E4, longer than anticipated to figure out the best solution. The hardware procurement list underwent various rounds of review and discussions, as did the overall cloud description. The selection of hardware is crucial and demands thorough analysis, as it represents a definitive investment with lasting implications. In conclusion, designing the physical environment underscores the complexity of integrating diverse perspectives while ensuring alignment with project objectives. Moving forward, the described hardware will be deployed to make it available to all project partners.

5 Sustainability

In order to correctly finish the present task, there was a great need to interact with other Work Packages. In fact, all partners needed to contribute to the discussion about computational resources, so that we could come to the most reasonable conclusion possible. In particular, partners from WP2, WP3, and WP4 were involved in the discussion, and this was a great opportunity for everybody to get a complete overview of the whole project.

6 Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

The present task was not included in any dissemination event yet.

6.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the project, the audience for this deliverable is:

✓	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

7 Detailed report on the deliverable

This section is devoted to describing the hardware and software that form the development environment for DECICE. The motivations underpinning the choices made during the project, which led to the selected configuration, are also illustrated. The section is organized as follows. Subsection 7.1 focuses on the hardware that will be purchased for the project. Technical information on the characteristics of each piece of equipment is supplied. An explanation of why this specific hardware will be bought is also provided. If a choice results from a discussion between partners, it is indicated. Some notes on the available budget and the cost of each item are finally reported. Subsection 7.2 illustrates the middleware software that will be installed on the machine. The strengths of each tool are listed. This helps the reader understand why these tools will be used to set up the environment.

7.1 Infrastructure and Resources

One of the goals of task 5.2 of DECICE is to design a development environment, where developers involved in the project will

- implement Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery (CI/CD) of their software
- run use cases and evaluate relative metrics listed in D5.1
- test and demonstrate the novel cloud management framework, which is under development
- integrate the different DECICE components

in an accessible and manageable way. To allow DECICE developers to carry out these tasks, the hardware and network of the development environment were selected to meet the following specifications:

- Flexibility (i.e. the ability to accommodate different demands, workloads, and configurations efficiently) - the needs might differ between tests, for example in terms of computational resources required;
- Heterogeneity (i.e. the presence of different hardware components) - to accommodate the development and test of as many scenarios as possible;
- Accessibility (i.e. the possibility of accessing the provided resources) - in order to facilitate partners and developers' interaction with the system.

To satisfy these requirements within the budget constraints provided by the project, the environment reported in Figure 1 has been designed. The proposed infrastructure features a master node, three worker nodes without accelerators, one worker node equipped with a Graphical Processing Unit (GPU), and several Edge Devices. Master and worker nodes are based on AMD x86_64 architecture to be as general as possible and because AMD offers an excellent trade off between price and performance as detailed in subsections 7.1.1, 7.1.2, and 7.1.3. There is only one single communication network. Indeed, the different components are connected only through a 100 Gbit/second Mellanox ethernet network. A 10 Gbit/second ethernet switch is also present to facilitate communication and data exchange within the network. Internet of Things (IoT) or edge devices are connected to a different subnet to simulate external devices.

The resulting cluster can adapt to various workloads and handle different levels of demands, making it a very **flexible** machine. Due to different types of nodes and multiple edge devices, the system is quite **heterogenous**. Thus, the machine closely resembles a cloud computing system and can easily support cloud and edge computing workloads. In addition to this, due to the characteristics of the hardware and network, whose specific details will be listed later, the cluster is also suitable for low latency High Performance Computing (HPC), High Throughput Computing (HTC), Machine Learning (ML), and Artificial Intelligence (AI) workloads. It is appropriate for the three Use Cases proposed in the project and for general users with versatile and adaptable applications. About the Use Cases, we note that D5.1 does not set severe constraints regarding the cloud system. In general, the three Use Cases require a high-end GPU (Use Cases 1, 2, and 3) and 1 TB storage (Use Case 3). The designed infrastructure meets and exceeds these requirements as detailed in subsections 7.1.1, 7.1.2, and 7.1.3.

The accessibility feature deserves a few more words. The machine will be accessible to partners only through a Virtual Private Network (VPN). This is because the server will be installed within the E4 Computer Engineering data center. The company has rigorous security policies and has adopted this solution for a long time to safeguard its servers from malicious attacks. Some of the partners have perceived this as a possible system limitation, which could eventually impede CI/CD and the exchange of data between edge devices and the cluster. E4 believes that the VPN itself does not inherently restrict the ability to set CI/CD pipelines, as long as the servers hosting code repositories are configured as VPN clients. Analogously, there are no problems in configuring edge devices outside E4 private network to connect to the cluster via VPN. Indeed, partners at Huawei and BigTri use these methods routinely. The open-source software openVPN will be used with its custom security protocol. This needs to be installed and properly configured with the relevant certificates. Certificates and credentials necessary to access the VPN will be provided to the partners via email, once they submit a request through this portal <https://e4company.atlassian.net/servicedesk/customer/portal/4/group/9/create/27>. Some partners would have preferred to access the machine through a bastion host. However, a bastion host would have meant profound changes to how E4 provides access to its data center, which could translate into severe delays for the project. Furthermore, for safety reasons, E4 would allow the connection only from a certain restricted number of fixed internet protocol (IP) addresses, which we believe would be even more problematic for the project. Once the VPN connection has been activated, DECICE developers will be able to access the machine via Secure Shell (SSH), either directly from the terminal on Unix/Linux local machines or through software such as openSSH on Windows local machines. If developers need to run applications using a Graphical User Interface (GUI), port forwarding must be enabled using, for instance, the `-X` option, which allows for X11 forwarding. It is important to mention that the VPN connection does not impede access to the external internet.

Before describing the hardware in detail, a small note on the network should be reported. As mentioned, the system is equipped with a 100 Gbit/second Mellanox ethernet network only. During the procurement, a more performant Infiniband network was also considered. Unfortunately, this would have increased the cost of the system beyond the available budget, so the idea was abandoned. However, we note that Infiniband is not necessary for cloud and edge workloads, which usually run inter-node. Thus, while Infiniband would have enlarged the scope of the computing infrastructure

allowing it to support also low latency HPC, it was deemed unnecessary to reach the objectives of DECICE.

The rest of the section will be dedicated to describing in detail the hardware resources that will form the system. We believe that the designed system represents the best option for testing DECICE framework developed within the project in conditions akin to production within the given budget constraints.

Finally, we inserted a description of the HAICGU cluster, made available by Huawei and already accessible by project partners. The description can be found in Appendix A. On the HAICGU cluster, partners can use and test cloud tools like KubeEdge, Sedna,⁷ and Volcano, for which a DECICE Seminar was previously organized.

DECICE DEVELOPMENT ENVIRONMENT LAYOUT

Figure 1: Development Environment Schema. This layout has a single ethernet network connecting the master node with the worker nodes and the GPU node. The IoT/Edge Devices are connected to a different subnet to simulate external devices.

7.1.1 Master node

The master node (or front-end machine) has multiple functions:

- Login node: all users trying to access the development environment do so by connecting to a VPN first and then by `ssh` on the login node;
- Management node: the administrator uses this server to manage all clusters with functions like node recovery and user authentication/authorization;
- Virtual machine provisioning;
- Container management;

- Monitor and control service;
- Shared storage server via NFS protocol;

The master node consists of a single socket server with:

- 1 x AMD Epyc 48-Core 7643 2.30 Ghz 256 MB 225 W
- 8 x DDR4-3200 Reg. ECC 32 GB module, for a total memory of 256 GB
- 2 x Micron 5400PRO 960 GB 2,5" SSD SATA DWPD 1.5, for the Linux operating system
- 3 x Micron 5400PRO 7.68 TB 2,5" SSD SATA DWPD 1.5, to share storage area via NFS
- 1 x Intel X710 10Gpbs DualPort SFP+

The master node features an AMD Epyc 7643 processor. This is part of the AMD Epyc 7003 series, also known as Milan. With 48 cores/processors with two threads each, AMD Epyc 7643 is very suitable for demanding workloads, including all the functions of a cloud master node. Its parallel processing and multithreading ability are also beneficial for cloud management software. AMD Epyc 7643 is a multi-purpose processor based on x86 architecture, which, for all the listed reasons and the fair cost, we deemed appropriate for the task.

The large amount of Random Access Memory (RAM) of the node (256 GB) will allow for the flawless management and orchestration of the cloud infrastructure. In particular, we expect this RAM size to ensure smooth operations and responsiveness of the master node. The amount has been determined considering that the master node will run the operative system (OS) and host cloud management software (from Kubernetes to OpenStack). Both OS and software consume RAM for their operations. While choosing the size, we also considered database caching and indexing. Databases will be employed to store configurations, metadata, and information in general. A large RAM reduces the need to retrieve information from slower storage devices. Since in a cloud system, RAM is also employed for tracking the state and monitoring the performance of the various resources (virtual machines, containers, storage, networks, ...); we are confident that the selected RAM size is also enough to process real-time data and make informed decisions about resource allocation, scaling and troubleshooting. This amount of RAM will ensure that incoming requests, such as user commands, resource provisioning, and scaling actions, will be processed promptly and the queue will be managed efficiently. It will also be able to handle Application Programming Interfaces (API) and administrator user interfaces for cloud management, thus guaranteeing a responsive and efficient user experience. Finally, we note that RAM based on DDR4 is the current industry standard.

Thanks to their low latency, the three 7.68 TB Solid State Drives (SSDs) SATA disks enable quick read and write operations. This characteristic also contributes to rapid application launches and file transfers. Compared to other technologies, such as Hard Disk Drives (HDDs), these disks are more reliable and less energy-demanding. SATA SSDs are compatible with many systems, and their installation is not complicated. SSDs with higher performance levels exist on the market. However, we considered them unnecessary to reach DECICE's goals. We believe the available storage space should be sufficient for planned software and applications. However, other five disks can be added to the system if more discs are needed. The disks will be connected via the Network File System (NFS) protocol. This widely supported cross-platform protocol allows virtual machines (VMs) or

nodes to access the same files or data. NFS guarantees more efficient storage utilization and easier maintenance. Its flexibility is a valuable feature in a cloud environment. Suppose more space is needed during the project. In that case, new storage can easily be added, and all connected clients can access the new capacity without changes to individual client configurations. Sharing the file system via NFS will simplify this operation if data migration is needed. NFS allows for configuring the file system, enabling snapshots and backups. This aspect is crucial to recover data in case of failures. Images of VMs and containers will be stored here so that they can be easily recovered. In summary, NFS offers many performance, scalability, and reliability advantages, so we chose this storage architecture for DECICE.

7.1.2 Worker nodes

Worker nodes, also known as compute nodes, provide the computing resources of the cloud system. They are responsible for running the virtual machines created by DECICE users. Each compute node must have a hypervisor, such as KVM, QEMU, VMware, or Hyper-V. The hypervisor ultimately enables the node to host and run VMs. It also allows multiple VMs to run on a single compute node, providing isolation and resource allocation for each VM.

The three worker nodes selected for DECICE consist of single-socket servers, each with:

- 1 x AMD Epyc 32-Core 7543P 2.80 Ghz 256MB 225 W
- 8 x DDR4-3200 Reg. ECC 32 GB module, for a total memory of 256 GB
- 1 x Kioxia CD8-R RI 960 GB NVMe U.2 PCI-Ex DWPD 1, for the Linux operating system
- 1 x Kioxia CD8-R RI 1.92 TB NVMe U.2 PCI-Ex DWPD 1, for local data
- 2 x Broadcom 10 Gigabit 10GBase-T

Also, the processor AMD Epyc 7643 featured in the worker nodes belongs to the AMD Epyc 7003 series code-named Milan. High core counts, performance, and scalability characterize all the processors in this series. With 32 physical cores and 64 threads, AMD Epyc 7643 can tackle parallel tasks and multi-threaded workloads. The architecture underpinning the processor, the so-called Zen 3, has improved instructions per clock (IPC) and overall performance compared to previous generations. The processor has a large L3 cache, providing fast access to frequently used data. AMD Epyc 7643 supports DDR4 memory. Thus, the high memory bandwidth is particularly suitable for memory-intensive applications. The availability of several Peripheral Component Interconnect express (PCIe) lanes would allow for high-speed connectivity with components, such as the storage, the networking adapters, ... It is power efficient with very good performance per watt. It supports the hardware virtualization extension AMD-V. The extension enhances virtualization efficiency by offloading certain tasks to the hardware, improving overall VM performance. Summarising, AMD Epyc 7643 is particularly suitable for data center and enterprise workloads. We believe that Epyc 7643 is a multi-purpose processor with an adequate number of cores and processing power for handling the computational workloads of VMs in the case of the specific Use Cases envisioned in DECICE and the case of general applications. It is better suited for virtualization and cloud environments than its direct Intel competitor (Intel Cascade Lake) due to the higher core count, better performance-per-euro, and

competitive memory bandwidth.

The large amount of RAM of the worker nodes (256 GB/node) will allow for running multiple VMs simultaneously.

Even if not massive, the local storage of each node is sufficient for temporary and local data. NonVolatile Memory express (NVMe) technology with a PCIe interface enables quick Input/Output (I/O) operations and results particularly useful for I/O-demanding applications.

The worker nodes were also selected to potentially facilitate horizontal scalability and allow the cloud infrastructure to grow by adding more nodes.

The presence of three nodes will allow us to implement redundancy at the compute node level if desired. Ultimately, this will enhance the reliability and availability of the cloud infrastructure.

7.1.3 GPU node

While standard worker nodes do not have any accelerators, the DECICE system will also feature a compute node with GPU. The GPU node will host the DECICE machine learning-based scheduling system, among other functions. This requirement comes from the Use Cases, in which ML tasks are to be executed. In particular, the GPU will accelerate scheduling decisions.

The GPU node consists of a single socket server with:

- 1 x AMD Epyc 32-Core 9334 2.7 Ghz 128 MB 210 W
- 12 x DDR5-4800 Reg. ECC 32 GB module, for a total memory of 384 GB
- 1 x Micron 5400PRO 960GB 2,5" SSD SATA DWPD 1.5
- 1 x Kioxia CD8-R RI 1.92 TB NVMe U.2 PCI-Ex DWPD 1, for local storage
- 1 x NVIDIA A30 24GB
- 1 x Mellanox CX-6 VPI Single-Port QSFP56 100Gb/s x16
- 1 x Intel X550 10 GbE DualPort 10Base-T Module

The AMD Epyc 9334 is part of the fourth generation of AMD processors, the Genoa series. The Genoa series processors present important improvements concerning processors belonging to the Milan family. In particular, the microarchitecture they are based on, the Zen 4 microarchitecture, features 29% more instructions per time unit compared to Zen 3. Moreover, the AMD Genoa series will feature AMD Infinity Architecture and AMD Infinity Guard technologies, which help minimize potential attack surfaces as software is booted, executed, and processes data. AMD Epyc 9334 supports the next RAM generation, DDR5, and has 12 memory channels. Indeed, the GPU node has more RAM than the non-accelerated worker nodes: 384 GB instead of 256 GB. A powerful Central Processing Unit (CPU) like the AMD Epyc 9334 in the GPU node is beneficial for managing data transfer, preprocessing, and overall system coordination in case of GPU-intensive workloads. For workloads that run partially on the GPU and partially on the CPU, such as database applications, virtualization, ..., the selected CPU will help improve the overall system performance.

The node is accelerated by an NVIDIA RTX A30 24GB GPU. This is based on the Ampere architecture, which brings performance and energy efficiency improvements to previous generations. A nice feature of this model is the large amount of VRAM and the high memory bandwidth for quick data transfer. Consequently, this GPU can easily handle large datasets and will be beneficial for reaching DECICE's goals. It has dedicated support for AI tasks, which can be very useful for speeding up scheduling decisions. The GPU has NVLink support, which could be a nice feature if more GPUs were added. The GPU card supports Multi-Instance GPU (MIG). This entails that the GPU can be partitioned in up to 4 GPU instances, each fully isolated with its own high-bandwidth memory, cache, and compute cores. MIG works with the selected middleware software for virtualization and containerization.

7.1.4 IoT/Edge Device

An Nvidia Jetson AGX Orin and two Raspberry Pi 5 complete the DECICE system. They will serve as edge devices to test the feasibility of the DECICE framework and are a significant component for making the overall cluster heterogeneous instead of homogeneous. The Pis features a quad-core ARM processor and 4 GB of RAM. Such edge devices will allow DECICE to expand its aims towards the compute continuum. They will run KubeEdge to connect to the cluster.

Other options, such as the IoT gateway ECU-150-12A1, have been previously considered. ECU-150-12A1 is characterized by excellent robustness, reliability, and stability. These features make it ideal for harsh environments. Since this is not the case with DECICE, the idea was discarded. In fact, it was thought that these types of devices would not have brought significant advantages compared to their cost. Indeed, the Raspberry Pis represents a very cost-effective solution for edge computing deployments. Their low cost allowed for having more than one edge device in the DECICE system. Besides being affordable, they are also compact, energy-efficient, versatile, and easy to use. All these features have made them very attractive for DECICE. In particular, they appear to be very suitable for IoT applications, which are one of the interests of the DECICE project. Initially, the idea was to get 4 Pis to simulate more edge nodes. However, eventually, the consortium agreed to get an edge node with a GPU to simulate more diverse scenarios. In fact, with an edge device equipped with a GPU, it is easier to perform parallel computation on the edge. This means that, for example, neural networks can be executed - even partially - on the edge. In conclusion, such choice allows for a wider set of possibilities during the task-scheduling process.

7.1.5 Ethernet Switch

The system is finalized by a switch to facilitate communication and data exchange within the network. The selected switch has 48 10 GbE SFP+ ports and 6 100 GbE uplink ports. The switch has a 2.16 Tbps switching capacity and delivers wire-speed switching performance on all 10 Gigabit and 100 Gigabit ports. The switch also supports the most advanced IPv6 management, IPv6 security, and IPv6 multicast control. We should point out that network performance was identified not to be critical for Use Cases: this choice was made to support fast management of the OpenStack cluster.

7.1.6 Budget

The project has a budget of 50,000 Euro to set up the development environment. The hardware described has been selected to serve the purposes of the project within the given budget. Individual prices can be seen in Table 1.

Master node	8,850.00 Euro
Worker node	5,405.00 Euro
GPU node	11,700.00 Euro
Jetson Edge Device	2,110.00 Euro
Raspberry Pi 5	116.00 Euro
Switch	8,197.00 Euro
Hosting	2,100.00 Euro

Table 1: Unit quotation for the selected hardware.

7.2 Middleware

Middleware software is another important development environment component besides hardware and network. This is crucial to facilitate communication, integration, and management of the different components of the cloud infrastructure. To facilitate the work of DECICE developers, the middleware software should be scalable, flexible, modular, and user-friendly. It should facilitate communication and coordination between distributed components, allowing them to work together seamlessly. It should support containerization technologies like Docker and container orchestration platforms like Kubernetes. This would allow for efficient deployment, scaling, and management of applications in cloud-native environments. It should be characterized by robust security features for protecting data and applications in the cloud. It should provide tools for monitoring resource usage, tracking errors, and generating logs. There should be integration with common DevOps tools and practices, such as Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery (CI/CD) pipelines, version control systems, and configuration management tools. It should also be compatible with multiple programming languages and frameworks, allowing developers to use the languages they are most comfortable with. Considering all these characteristics and the E4's long-time experience in this framework, we have selected several middleware tools to complete the DECICE system. They are described in the rest of the section.

7.2.1 Bare metal provisioning and node recovery

Foreman is an open-source infrastructure management tool that provides a web-based interface for provisioning, configuring, and managing physical and virtual servers. It offers several advantages for IT administrators and DevOps teams in automating and managing infrastructure. It supports the provisioning of both physical and virtual machines and excels in bare-metal provisioning, allowing for the automated deployment of operating systems on new hardware. It integrates with configuration management tools such as Puppet, Ansible, and Chef. This enables automatic configuration and ensures that systems are consistently configured according to defined policies, reducing manual intervention and ensuring reproducibility. It provides tools for managing the complete lifecycle of systems, from initial provisioning to ongoing maintenance, updates, and decommissioning. This

includes features for tracking changes, applying updates, and managing system retirement. It integrates with popular virtualization platforms, including VMware, oVirt, libvirt, and OpenStack. This allows for unified management of both physical and virtual environments from a single interface. Foreman integrates with external services such as DNS, DHCP, and monitoring tools. This facilitates a seamless workflow. Foreman supports various operating systems, making it suitable for heterogeneous environments. It allows for the management of hosts running different operating systems and distributions. It also grants node recovery through the image backup system. For all these reasons, at E4, we have adopted Foreman since 2016 and used it to install thousands of servers. We believe that our long-time experience is a plus for DECICE, and we plan to use Foreman to deploy DECICE cluster.

The system will be deployed and maintained by E4 personnel using Foreman. Hence, Foreman will be completely transparent to DECICE developers. In case they have special requirements about setting the cluster up, then they can make their request by opening a ticket here: <https://e4company.atlassian.net/servicedesk/customer/portal/4/group/9/create/27>.

7.2.2 CI/CD Toolchain

In DECICE, we plan to set up CI/CD pipelines for applications using Jenkins and GitLab. Pipelines automate testing and reporting on isolated changes in a more extensive code base in real-time and facilitate the integration of disparate branches of the code into a main branch. They also rapidly detect defects in a code base, build the software, automate testing of their builds, prepare the code base for deployment (delivery), and ultimately deploy code to containers and virtual machines, as well as bare metal and cloud servers. A list of steps of a CI/CD pipeline can be seen in Figure 2.

Jenkins is an open-source CI/CD automation software DevOps tool written in Java. Jenkins is open-source, highly extendable, and customizable compared to similar tools. It is widely adopted, so it has a very large user base. It is characterized by a rich ecosystem of plugins that cover a wide range of functionalities. These plugins integrate Jenkins with various tools, version control systems, build systems, deployment platforms, and more, enhancing its versatility and adaptability to different environments. With Jenkins, the workload could be distributed across multiple build agents, resulting in efficient utilization of resources and faster build times. It is relatively simple to install and configure. Its user-friendly web-based interface simplifies the setup process, making it accessible to beginners and experienced users. It integrates seamlessly with various version control systems like Git, SVN, and Mercurial. This integration automatically triggers builds based on code changes, improving collaboration and continuously testing code changes. Jenkins is language-agnostic and supports various programming languages and build tools. This flexibility allows development teams to use their preferred languages and tools within the CI/CD pipeline. Like in the case of Foreman, E4 has a lot of experience managing projects with Jenkins, which was considered an added value.

There are several commercial versions of Jenkins. We refer here to the upstream open-source project.

GitLab is a web-based tool for DevOps. Its main functionalities are Git repository manager, CI/CD pipelines, code review, and issue tracking. It can manage the end-to-end software development process, from version control to deployment and monitoring.

Figure 2: CI/CD pipeline. Adapted from <https://katalon.com/resources-center/blog/ci-cd-pipeline>.

It has more features compared to similar tools such as GitHub or BitBucket. For instance, it includes built-in CI/CD pipelines, container registry, code review tools, issue tracking, and more, thus enabling teams to manage their entire workflow within a single platform. Through the built-in CI/CD system, developers can automate the testing, building, and deployment of their applications directly within the GitLab environment. This means there is no need for external CI/CD tools, and setting up automated pipelines is simpler. It is integrated with Docker, which is particularly useful for containerization projects for application deployment. Within GitLab, code review and collaboration are made more accessible. It has built-in issue-tracking and project management tools. This is quite useful for projects like DECICE: indeed, tasks, milestones, and releases could be managed within the same platform where the code is hosted. Static websites could be created directly from the repository. This could be handy for building project documentation websites, for instance.

In this project, we will use the Community Edition of GitLab, which is open-source and free. GitLab is already used by partners, currently hosted by GWDG, and accessible through Academic Cloud Infrastructure.

To set up a CI/CD pipeline using Jenkins and GitLab, provided that Jenkins has been installed and configured on the cluster, the following steps must be carried out:

1. Create a GitLab repository to host the application and push there the application source
2. Define a pipeline using a Jenkinsfile stored in the GitLab; the file must specify stages (checkout, build, test, and deploy), steps, and configurations of the pipeline
3. Configure GitLab to trigger the Jenkins pipeline automatically when changes get pushed into

the repository

4. Set up a webhook in GitLab that points to the Jenkins server and triggers the Jenkins job whenever a new commit is pushed
5. Set up the automated tests to verify correctness and performance
6. Set up alerts in case of build failures, quality issues, or other important events

7.2.3 Virtualization

Virtualization is essential for cloud computing as it allows for the efficient use of physical resources by abstracting them into virtual instances. In our case, virtualization will be achieved using OpenStack. This choice facilitates the deployment of different DECICE framework instances, which is very helpful for development and testing.

OpenStack is an open-source cloud computing platform developed and maintained by a diverse and rich community of developers and organizations. It provides infrastructure as a service (IaaS) in private and public clouds. An OpenStack deployment comprises several components that provide APIs to access infrastructure resources. Currently, we are considering the OpenStack components described as follows.

- **Nova.** This is the computing engine of OpenStack. It allows users to create and manage VMs. It is responsible for provisioning, scheduling, and managing compute resources. It supports different hypervisors; in this project, QEMU, which is fully supported, will be used.
- **Neutron.** It offers an API for networking functions (interfaces, routers, switches, ports, floating IP addresses, ...). It allows users to define and customize their VMs network configuration by integrating with traditional networks and using existing protocols.
- **Swift.** It is the object storage system. It is designed so that users can store and retrieve large unstructured data.
- **Cinder.** It provides storage volumes for VM instances. This storage persists beyond the VM lifecycle. In summary, Cinder allows users to create, attach, and detach storage volumes to their VMs according to their needs.
- **Keystone.** Keystone handles user authentication, roles, and permission to access OpenStack services.
- **Horizon.** It is the web-based dashboard of OpenStack. It is a user-friendly interface for administrators and end users to deal with OpenStack resources. It allows for managing resources, launching instances, and configuring settings.
- **Glance.** The component takes care of VM image management by handling VM snapshots or templates. With Glance, users can discover, register, and retrieve VM images.
- **Heat.** This enables users to define and manage templates for their VMs. It is not essential, but it could help DECICE developers.

- Trove. It is a database service that allows users to deploy databases in an automated and scalable manner. This is an optional component, but it might be useful.
- Octavia. It is a load-balancing service to distribute network traffic across resources. This component is optional but has been required by partners at GWDG.
- Magnum. It helps to deploy and manage container orchestration engines within OpenStack. This component is optional; however, it will simplify the usage of Kubernetes on an OpenStack VM (see discussion at the end of 7.2.4).

OpenStack is easily scalable, allowing the addition of more resources. It is very flexible and API-driven, so users can easily interact and manage cloud resources, and automation with other tools and services is also possible. Thanks to its modular architecture, only components deemed necessary (as listed above) need to be deployed. It integrates with Jenkins for CI/CD pipelines. OpenStack has been adopted in E4 for quite some time. The company has gained experience in automatically deploying the tool on Rocky Linux. We believe that this expertise is an added value for DECICE.

Previously, we considered using oVirt instead of OpenStack. **oVirt** is a free, open-source virtualization management platform. It was founded by Red Hat as a community project on which Red Hat Virtualization is based. However, its scope was considered too narrow for a larger-scale project like DECICE. Indeed, OpenStack provides a broader set of services. oVirt is less modular and flexible than OpenStack. We also felt that OpenStack would have supported multiple users and VMs better than oVirt because multi-tenancy underpins OpenStack's design. Indeed, maintaining isolation between user resources and data is important in a project like DECICE with multiple partners and multiple objectives/subprojects.

Creating and using VM instances with OpenStack is relatively straightforward. A web-based interface hosted on the master node and accessible using the IP address of the master node allows users to create and manage instances, security groups, volumes, images, and more. Once a VM is created with its set of computing resources, its OS, its storage, its network and other resources, the user will be able to access the VM via `ssh`, granted that appropriate security group rules were set when the instance was created. In particular, it is crucial to associate an SSH key pair with the VM instance during the creation process. The private key created in this way will be used for authentication.

OpenStack also allows the creation of a snapshot of the VM. Once the instance has been closed, the user needs to access the online dashboard, select the desired instance, and create a snapshot by clicking on the link "Create Snapshot". The snapshot of the instance will now become visible under the Images tab.

7.2.4 Containerization

Kubernetes or **K8s** is an open-source container orchestration platform for automating the deployment, scaling, and management of containerized applications. It is considered the standard for container orchestration and is widely adopted in both development and production environments. It works with the container runtime Docker and others. Through K8s API, users can declare the desired state of their applications and infrastructure. The platform then ensures that the actual state matches the declared state. It continuously monitors the health of applications and restarts or

Figure 3: Schema representing the interaction between a user and the computational resources. E4 is responsible for installing and managing the tools and providing support to users throughout all the login phases. Each support request should be sent through the specific ticketing platform.

replaces failed containers. It is extensible and can be integrated with cloud providers, monitoring solutions, and CI/CD tools. Kubernetes is appropriate for managing microservices-based applications. It facilitates deployments in cloud environments. It is suited for edge computing and can easily manage applications at the network's edge where resources may be limited. It integrates seamlessly with CI/CD pipelines.

Besides K8s, the standard unmodified distribution of Kubernetes, we have also considered containerization via K3s.

K3s is the lightweight Kubernetes distribution created by Rancher Labs. It is fully certified by the Cloud Native Computing Foundation (CNCF), which maintains Kubernetes. K3s is highly available and production-ready. It has a very small binary size and very low resource requirements. K3s is a fully compliant Kubernetes distribution with the following enhancements:

- Packaged as a single binary.
- The lightweight storage backend is based on SQLite3 as the default storage mechanism. etcd3, MySQL, and Postgres are also available.
- Wrapped in a simple launcher that handles much of the complexity of TLS and options.
- Secure by default with reasonable defaults for lightweight environments.

Compared to K8s, K3s has more straightforward installation and operation. It requires fewer resources, and it might be simpler to use. It is particularly suitable for edge computing and IoT deployments. It can be deployed on single-node clusters and work with limited resources. However, it was thought that the vanilla version of Kubernetes with all its components would be more suitable

for the DECICE project. Additionally, it was felt that K8s would ensure the best compatibility with the development of DECICE.

Both K8s and K3s can be used on bare metal or VMs. Both options have advantages and disadvantages. On the one hand, bare metal allows for better performance and more efficient resource utilization due to the absence of a hypervisor layer, but managing resources may be more complicated. On the other hand, virtualized environments are more flexible and scalable. A definite decision for DECICE has not yet been taken and will be the object of further discussion. We aim to decide when the procurement will be over.

Kubernetes will be completed by a private container registry, which will be stored on the shared NFS disk of the master node.

Container orchestration will be extended to the edge devices via KubeEdge. **KubeEdge** integrates with K8/K3 to extend workloads to the edge. By using KubeEdge with Kubernetes, there will be only one management interface. This ensures consistency in deploying, scaling, monitoring, and updating applications across edge and cloud environments. Furthermore, it simplifies operations and reduces management overhead. The integration between edge and cloud environments running K8/K3 is straightforward and allows data synchronization and workload migration between the devices and the cloud environment. A nice feature of KubeEdge is the support of offline operations. This means that devices can keep working even when not connected to the main development machine.

7.3 Timeframe for implementation

The steps into which the work can be divided consist of four different steps:

1. Ordering materials and waiting time for delivery. Here, the slowest element determines the overall waiting time for the next step.
2. Systems integration and physical installation in the E4 lab by E4 personnel.
3. Installation and configuration of the DECICE framework (middleware) by E4 personnel.
4. Setup of the CI/CD pipelines to use the development environment by DECICE developers to run tests and benchmarks.

In our experience, the time required for phase 1 from the time of order can take up to 4 months. The time needed for phase two should be considered from 2 to 4 weeks. The third phase can be anticipated before the proposed system is brought online on in-house development virtual machines. The overall duration is challenging to estimate, also depending on the level of features to be implemented and feedback received from users; we can consider it as continuous work throughout the duration of the project, with a minimum time to get the first release into production of about six months.

A Additional Resources - the HAICGU cluster

Huawei AI and Computing at Goethe University (HAICGU) is a cluster based on Huawei HPC solution. This cluster is installed at the Goethe University of Frankfurt and maintained by Open Edge and HPC initiative (OEHI). The Goethe University Frankfurt is part of the National High-Performance Computing Alliance.

The following list shows the currently installed nodes and servers of the cluster:

1. 28x Standard Compute Node – TaiShan 200 (Model 2280)
 - 2 x Kunpeng 920 processor (ARMv8 AArch64; 64 cores; 2.6GHz; 180W)
 - 28GB main memory (16x 8GB, one DIMM per channel)
 - 1x 100Gbit/s EDR Infiniband HCA
2. 1x Development Compute Node – TaiShan 200 (Model 2280)
 - 2 x Kunpeng 920 processor (ARMv8 AArch64; 64 cores; 2.6GHz; 180W)
 - 128GB main memory (16x 8GB, one DIMM per channel)
 - 1x 100Gbit/s EDR Infiniband HCA
 - 2 x 960GB SSD SATA 6Gb/s
3. 2x IO Node – TaiShan 200 (Model 5280)
 - Metadata storage: 2x 960GB SSD SATA 6Gb/s (RAID 1)
 - Object storage: 32x 1.2 TB HDD SAS 12Gb/s; 10.000rpm (RAID 10)
 - Mgmt. storage: 4x 1.2 TB HDD SAS 12Gb/s; 10.000rpm (RAID 10)
4. 1x AI Training Node – Atlas 800 (Model 9000)
 - 4x Kunpeng 920 processor (ARMv8 AArch64)
 - Neural Processing Unit (NPU): 8x Huawei Ascend 910 with 32 AI cores and 32GB HBM2 memory
 - 1024GB main memory: 32x 32GB DDR4 2933MHz RDIMM
 - Local storage: 2x 960 GB SSD SATA 6Gb/s
 - Data storage: 4x 3.2TB SSD NVMe
5. 1x AI Inference Node – Atlas 800 (Model 3000)
 - 2 x Kunpeng 920 processor (ARMv8 AArch64)
 - 512GB main memory: 16x 32GB DDR4 2933 MHz RDIMM
 - Local storage: 2x 960GB SSD SATA 6Gb/s
 - Data storage: 4 x 960GB SSD SATA 6Gb/s

- GPU: 5x Atlas 300 AI Inference Card; 32GB; PCIe3.0 x16

6. 2x Atlas 500 A2 Edge Station

Ascend 310 Processor:

- One DaVinci V300 Core (The dominant frequency at 20 TOPS is 1.224 GHz, and that at 8 TOPS is 0.5 GHz.)
- Four TAISHANV200M processor cores (The dominant frequency at 20 TOPS is 1.6 GHz, and that at 8 TOPS is 1.0 GHz.)

Compute power:

- Half precision (FP16): 4/10 TFLOPS
- Integer precision (INT8): 8/20 TOPS

Processor memory: LPDDR4x, 12 GB, 96-bit, 4266 Mbit/s

Storage:

- Onboard 32 GB eMMC (used for storing OS and application software)
- One 8 TB 3.5-inch SATA drive
- One slot for a microSD card, with a maximum rate of HS400 and a maximum capacity of 2 TB
- One slot for a 2242 or 2280 SATA M.2 SSD

The nodes are connected via a non-blocking EDR Infiniband 100Gbit/s fabric for high bandwidth, low latency communication as well as an Ethernet network for deployment and management.

Open-source software is used for the cluster software environment. The cluster is built on Rocky Linux 8 with SLURM as a job scheduler. Lustre in combination with ZFS provides a high-performance parallel filesystem to the users. EasyBuild is used extensively to install and configure software packages: GCC, OpenMPI, Python, SciPy and others. The AI software stack is built on top of Huawei's CANN (Compute Architecture for Neural Networks) toolkit, which will support AI frameworks like TensorFlow, PyTorch, ONNX and Mindspore.